

5 **Title**
The konstruktive Electronics Standard

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20 **Abstract**

25 This document provides dimension and connectivity information for modular electronics circuits (modules), which are at the heart of the non-proprietary *konstructive Electronics Standard*. The motivation for this standard is compose-ability and the reuse of electronic components and modules. Projects implemented using the standard easily transition from prototype to final assembly, and can range from simple electronic circuits to distributed computing systems.

30 Each module consists of electronic components on a castellated printed circuit board. The dimensions of these modules are based on a 12 mm grid. Using this grid, modules with 12 mm * 12 mm, 12 mm * 24 mm, 24 mm * 24 mm, and so forth, can be created. Modules can be rectangular, but modules can also have grid-dimensioned cut-outs to interface with inset modules. The castellated conducting surfaces between modules can be bridged by pins or by solder, thus allowing ephemeral and permanent assemblies, and hybrids thereof.

35 The edge connecting surfaces consist of half-vias with a center-to-center spacing of 2 mm and a diameter of 1 mm. The corners of a rectangular module consist of quarter vias. Thus, four modules intersect to form a conductive ring (3 mm diameter), which can also be used to fasten modules. As all corner vias within a module are electrically connected, interfacing these vias creates a common electrical ground between adjacent modules. Another set of four pairs of vias (diameter 1 mm) is located 3 mm inset from each module corner and can distribute separate voltage and ground, if necessary.

45 **Keywords**

- electronics
- electronic hardware
- circular economy
- 50 • conviviality
- planned obsolescence
- reuse
- right-to-hack
- right-to-tinker
- 55 • right-to-innovate
- right-to-repair
- right-to-reuse
- right-to-share
- sustainability
- 60 • sustainable design
- open innovation
- open technologies
- tools of conviviality
- 65 • standardization

Motivation

70 The non-proprietary *konstructive Electronics Standard* was devised for creating electronic and computational devices that have the characteristics of *konstructive* tools [1]. A particular aspect that *The Standard* address, is the conservation of resources. However, as a non-proprietary standard, there are no limitations on using *The Standard*.

75 *PCB*

Most of current electronics are implemented using printed circuit boards (PCBs). Decades of developments have made the production of PCBs a largely automated process that is time-efficient and cost-efficient. However, the ease with which circuit boards can be
80 manufactured, comes at an enormous costs in the form of electronic waste.

Modularity

Modularization is a major, yet largely ignored strategy for avoiding electronic waste.
85 Modularized electronics would allow the reuse of parts in order to repair, customize and update electronic and computational equipment. One must consternate, however, that industry has very little interest in modularization, as this would limit the stream of meant-to-break and meant-to-be obsolescent products they make. Thus, we are in a situation where one single broken component - out of a thousand working components - will result in
90 replacing the entire electronic circuitry, or the entire equipment. This business model has not found strong opposition.

Governmental regulators have largely ignored modularization as a strategy for limiting electronic waste. Instead, the focus is on the collection of electronic waste, that aims to
95 reclaim embedded resources. Unfortunately, these reclaiming efforts are extremely inefficient, as only metals/semiconductors are valuable enough to be recovered. Consequently and farcically, the metal reclaimed from thousands of still perfectly functional electronic components, is used to manufacture identical new electronic components.

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Design Principles

Principles formulated in *The konstruktive Manifesto* [1] are applied here to guide the design and use of modules and module assemblies.

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Less

When thinking about designing a new module, one should check first, if there are no suitable modules already available. It is always possible to put more specific functionality on a module using specific components, but that misses the point of *konstruktive*. The *konstruktive way* is to rather consider using two existing modules than to create a new one.

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Cost

Component prices are usually a major factor when designing throw-away electronics. Traditionally, one would select the cheapest components to get by. For *konstruktive* electronics the thinking is different, because modules can be fully reused. This turns a liability (electronic waste) into an asset (*konstruktive* electronics retain their value). Therefore, it makes sense to use quality components when designing modules even when they are more expensive.

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Energy

Energy efficiency in electronics is flawed concept, as only “operating energy efficiency” is addressed. Thinking about energy efficiency, requires the assessment of all the energy embodied in the electronics, which includes the energy that went into making the electronic components (from mining to production), as well as the energy that will be used to maintain the electronics and the energy required to recover used resources. Surprising to many, the amount of energy used in operation during the entire lifetime of most electronic component, is only a tiny fraction of the embodied energy.

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More

When designing *konstruktive* solutions, it can make good sense to use modules that seem over-powered for the task, if they already exist. For example, using an MCU that has peripherals that are not used at all in the application seems to be a wasteful. Maybe there are cheaper MCUs – keep ‘Less is More’ in mind. Maybe there are more “energy-efficient solutions” – keep ‘Energy’ in mind. So, if there is a module that can do the job, *konstruktive* electronics gives you the freedom to ignore ‘throw-away-cost’ and ‘operation energy efficiency’.

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Proprietary standards

It is good practice to avoid proprietary standards whenever possible. These standards can (and usually will) change as they can be used to increasing profits by making hardware obsolete. However, expired proprietary standards that have proven themselves will no longer change, and these standards may be very valuable.

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Producer lock-in

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There are good reasons to avoid producer lock-in. When the only producer of a component goes out of business, all modules that uses it must be retired, and consequently all module assemblies that use the module become unrepairable. Furthermore, there is no room for negotiation about pricing or conditions – you are “locked in”. It is good practice to check if there are drop-in-replacements available from multiple producers, before selecting any component for a new module.

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Documentation

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Good documentation is a requirement to ensure that electronics can be repaired, reused and shared. Every electronics module should have documentation that details the modules that have been used, and ideally also how to diagnose faulty components and modules, and carry out repairs, modifications or updates that may be expected.

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Simplicity

Keeping things simple is a goal that is not easy to achieve. It takes a lot more time and effort to develop a simple solution. However, the benefits of keeping things simple are worth the toil. Simplicity ensures conservation of time and resources, and furthers convivial creativity.

170 **Specification**

175 **Overview**

The physical dimensions of the *konstruktive Electronic Standard (The Standard)* is based on “*konstruktive - A Millimetric, Recursive, base-Twelve Norm for the Construction of Physical Objects*” [2], which has a base dimensions of 1 mm a grid dimension of 12 mm.

180 *Module sizes*

185 The smallest electronic module size is a (nominal) 12 mm x 12 mm module (Figure 1). By extending this grid, larger modules (such as 12 mm x 24 mm, 12 x 36 mm, or 24 mm x 24 mm, 24 mm x 48 mm, or 48 mm x 48 mm, and so forth) can be constructed, which can interface with other modules. The modules can be rectangular in shape, but also contain cut-outs that align with the 12 mm grid (Figure 2).

Castellated PCB

190 Module PCBs can have thicknesses between 1 mm and 2 mm, and can be multi-layered. The modules are implemented on PCBs with castellated edges, which expose the through-hole conducting surfaces of vias. There are also defined position located inside the module in proximity to the module corners. Together these conducting surfaces allow to interface modules with each other.

195 *Placement of Components*

The Standard only specifies the placement of interfacing vias. Best practice for the placement of components and layering of the PCB should be applied.

200 *Functional grouping*

205 On a module, power and signal via surfaces are partitioned to different parts of the board. Via surfaces that interface with power (voltage and ground) are located at the corners of the module (both, peripheral and inset), while via surfaces that interface with electronic signals are located on the edges of the castellated PCB.

Common Ground & Mounting Hole

210 The four quarter vias of four interfacing modules form a complete via with a diameter of 3 mm, that has two functions. Firstly, the via carries a common ground between boards, and secondly the via can also be used as a mounting hole.

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Figure 1. Dimensions of a 12 x 12 mm module (top view). The four via surfaces on each edge carry electronic signals. The corners are quarter vias carrying ground. Inset from each corner are (optional) via pairs that provide local power (voltage and ground). Note that the (optional) clearance range is indicated in light grey, with a maximum clearance resulting in a 11.5 mm x 11.5 mm module.

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Figure 2. Module size and connectivity. Modules with the unit grid size (12 mm) interface with each other through four edge surfaces and corner surfaces (white gaps between boards). Modules with different grid sizes (shown in different colors) can interface with one another. The upper 24 mm x 24 mm (purple) module is a composite module that includes a 12 mm x 12 mm module (also purple). In the upper half of the figure, modules have openings implemented at grid intervals, while modules in the bottom half only have openings at the corners of the module. Where the two types of modules (grid openings / corner openings) interface, some edge openings face corner/grid openings.

Power Surfaces

250 Modules that carry active components (requiring a supply of power) have dedicated via
surfaces that are located within the corners of modules. A module can have several of these
surfaces, to support several active components with different power requirement. The
ground that these active components use can be the common ground that is shared between
255 modules, or an alternative ground that is specific to the active component. Modules that do
not have active components, are not require to have inset power surfaces.

Signal Surfaces

260 Signals between modules are transferred through half-via surfaces at the edge of a modules.
A recess between conducting surfaces ensures that conducting surfaces of neighbouring
modules do not make accidental contact. This common recess distance (0.5 mm) of edge
surfaces ensures that modules with different module-to-module clearances remain
interoperable.

Connecting Surfaces

265 Modules are electrically connected by bridging the castellated via surfaces of neighbouring
modules. A major consideration for the sizing of the recess of castellated surfaces was the
intention to create an electronics system that allows the seamless transition from prototype
270 to final assembly. Ephemeral connections can be established with flexible pins, while for
more permanent assemblies the gap between modules can be bridged with solder.

Clearance between Modules

275 The half-clearance between module edges ranges between 0 (nil) to 0.25 mm, the latter is
also the distance by which edge surfaces are recessed from the grid. The difference in
clearance does not impact on edge surfaces interfacing with one another, as the recess
distances for the signal surfaces is independent of the clearance between boards.

Nominal Module Size vs Actual Module Size

280 Application of a 0.25 mm clearance to a module changes the module size from the nominal
12 mm grid. For example, the maximum and minmum edge-to-edge distances of sqaure
modules are 12 mm, 24 mm, 48 mm x 48 mm and 11.5 mm and 23.5 mm, 47.5 respectively.
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Nomenclature of Conducting Surfaces

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The conductive surfaces that facilitate the supply of power and the transfer of electronic signals have names that are based on the first letter of the four cardinal compass directions (N, n – top, W, w – left, S, s – bottom, E, e – right).

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Upper-case letters indicate castellated conducting surfaces on the module edge and corners. Lower case letters indicate via locations within the board.

G_global (*Corner Peripheral Ground Surfaces*)

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Four ground conducting surfaces are located at the module corners, and are labeled in upper-case letters. These surfaces are called NW, SW, SE, NE. Alternatively, if it is desired to emphasize that these surfaces carry ground, they can be called G_NW, N_SW, G_SE and G_NE.

G_local and V_local (*Corner inset Power Surfaces*)

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Four pairs of conducting surfaces (vias) can be located inset from the corners to supply power (ground and voltage). These surfaces are labeled with lower case-letters (nw, sw, se, ne), when referring to the pair. Underscored prefixes indicate if the via carries ground (G_nw, G_sw, G_se, G_ne) or voltages (V_nw, V_sw, V_se, V_ne).

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Signal (*Edge surfaces*)

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The signal carrying surfaces are identified with numbers (that increase from N to S and from W to E), post-fixed with N, W, S, E, which indicates the side of the board (e.g. 1W, 1S). If it is desired to emphasize that a surface carries a signal the name can be pre-fixed with “Sig_” (e.g. Sig_1E).

Coordinate System

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The signal surfaces establish a coordinate system that can be used to describe the position of vias or other features. In this system, the first number is the coordinate in N-to-S direction and the second number is coordinate in the W-to-E direction. For example, on a 12 mm x 12 mm module, the center of the NW via is at (-0.5/-0.5) and the center of the SE via is at (5.5/5.5) (Figure 3).

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For a given board it is possible to replace positions on the edge with the edge name. For example on 24 mm x 24 mm module via position at (10.5/5.5) can also be indicated as (E/5.5) (Figure 3).

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All conducting surfaces on a board that are not “corner peripheral surfaces (e.g. NW)”, “corner inset surfaces (e.g. G_nw and V_ne)”, or “edge surfaces (1E)” are named using their function and coordinates. For example, a resistor via is called R220kOhm(2/3.75), when positioned at (2/3.75).

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Figure 3. Names and location of conducting surfaces (12 mm x 12 mm module).

A top view of 12 mm x 12 mm module is schematically represented.

Corner peripheral surfaces (NW, SW, SE, NE) carry common ground (black)

Corner inset surfaces (nw, sw, se, ne) carry power. Matching local ground (purple)

and local voltage (red) surfaces are labeled with G and V prefixes (e.g. G_nw and V_nw). Note the square shape of the V_nw pad, used for asserting module orientation.

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Signal surfaces (blue) N, W, S, E are prefixed with their coordinates (1N to 4N, 1W to 4W, 1S to 4S, 1E to 4E) .

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Figure 4. Nomenclature and location of vias on a module with cut-out.

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The dimensions of the composite module is 24 mm x 24 mm and the cutout dimensions are 12 mm x 12 mm. All corner surfaces (peripheral and offset) are present and labeled, besides SW and sw surfaces (which are eliminated by the cut-out). Surfaces that interface with the cut-out section of the module are labeled only with their coordinates. Coordinates increase from N-to-S and from W-to-E. Surfaces that are on the edges of the module can use the boundary designation as the coordinate (e.g. $G_{global}(5.5/S)$). Boundary designations can also be used for inset surfaces (e.g. $v_{local}(se)$ as alternative to $v_{local}(10/10)$ or v_{ne}).

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Board Orientation

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To mark the orientation of a module v_{nw} , which is located at (1/1) must be implemented as a square pad (as part of a via or not) on the top face of a module. All other v_{local} surfaces have round pads and no square pads should be implemented at a position that could be interpreted as (1/1). A orientation-marking (1/1) square pad must be implemented

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even if there is no via or connection to the pad.

Beyond the Uni-Grid-Size Module

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When modules span more than one grid unit and/or are not square (due to grid-dimensioned cut-outs) the labeling rules developed for the unit module have to be reconsidered.

Cut-out

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A module may contain a cut out, when the main functionality of the board is usually supplemented by an electronic circuit with changing properties. For example, a cut out could contain an application-specific power supply, or bank of resistors. Labeling for a 24 mm x 24 mm board with grid-dimensioned cut-out is presented in Figure 4 and also discussed in the legend. The 12 mm x 12 mm cut-out includes the SW corner of the 24 mm x 24 mm module, therefore the respective surfaces (SW, v_{sw} , G_{sw}) are not on the board, and no “stand-in” vias are assigned.

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Ground Surface vs Signal Surfaces

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A 24 mm x 24 mm module (Figure 4) can have two different features along the edge that coincide with the grid interface.

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One option is to place a “corner” (G_{global}) half via at the grid unit interval. This is the case on the E edge, which consequently has two sets of 4-Signal surfaces (1E to 4E and 7E to 10E) separated by a “corner” G_{global} surface (E/5.5) (Figure 4).

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The other option is to place two signal vias adjacent to the grid unit interval. This is the case for the N edge, which has 10 signal surfaces (1N to 10N) (Figure 4).

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What determines whether a G_{global} via or two signal vias are placed along the edge of a module? Here, function has priority over form. If a module is designed to transfer data, and is part of a computing cluster interacting with similar modules with the same grid, then signal vias are the logical choice. If there is no expectation that a continuous bank of signal vias are needed, and connection with differently-dimensioned modules is expected, then including “corners” (G_{global}) is desirable, as this provides more options to interface with (smaller) modules.

Conducting surfaces – Positions and Dimensions

420 G_global

Surfaces that carry G_global are located at the four corners of a rectangular module. Each connecting surface possesses a quarter section of a circular via (radius of 3 mm) that includes a 3.5 mm x 3.5mm pad (on both sides of the PCB). When the corners of four modules interface with one another, they form a complete via / circular hole.

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G_global from other modules can make contact with the inside part of a via or through the associated via pads at the top/bottom surface of the module.

430 The four G_global surfaces of a rectangular module are electrically connected to one another. This connectivity is used to transfer G_global between different parts of a module, and distribute G_global to neighbouring modules.

435 While the center of the signal carrying vias is offset, the center of the G_global vias is positioned exactly on the grid. This is crucial, so four modules intersecting via sections form a mounting hole (3 mm diameter). Through these mounting holes, a fastener (such as screw) can hold modules in place, and also distribute G_global between adjacent boards (if the fastener is conductive).

440 G_local and V_local (*Local Power Surfaces*)

Power is supplied to a module via paired local power vias G_local and V_local. The position of V_local is 3 mm inset from the 12 mm grid. As a consequence modules that are larger than 12 mm x 12 mm may have V_locals located along the edge and inside the board, wherever the 3 mm grid distance is achieved. For example, a 24 mm x 24 mm board has 2 * 2 * 4 potential V_local positions (Figure 5). Here, we can distinguish between primary power surfaces located inset from the corners, secondary power surfaces, inset from the edges, and tertiary power surfaces places further inside of the grid.

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450 Every module with active components must have G_nw and V_nw surfaces, where the G_nw is usually continuous with G_global of a module. When there are active components present that require a different power supply, a separate V_local (and G_local) can be implemented on the module. If there is space on the board available, all primary V_local and G_local should be implemented and G_local and G_local should be continuous with G_global when possible.

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If there is sufficient space, the G_local and V_local surfaces should be implemented as a via, as a via provides more flexibility for connections (pins, solder-filled to create pad).

460 Every module must have a V_nw surface, implemented as a via with a square pad or stand alone square pad (sized 1.5 mm x 1.5 mm) on top, while all other V_local must have round pads, so the unique square pad can be used to determine the orientation of a module.

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Figure 5. Positions of local power surfaces.

All v_{local} positions on a 24 mm x 24 mm board are shown in color along with paired G_{local} (grey). v_{local} is inset 3 mm (in N-S and W-E direction) from the 12 mm grid (indicated with black lines). Primary location for v_{local} are shown in blue (corner), secondary locations are shown in green (edge), and tertiary locations are shown in red (middle).

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Figure 6. A NW corner of a module showing with of via pad surfaces.

Pads are shown in red. Note that the inset surface (V_{nw}) has a square pad (top) and a round pad (bottom, dashed line).

`v_local`

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Conducting surfaces for `v_local` are implemented as vias (diameter 1mm, pad diameter 1.5 mm), or as pads (diameter 1.5) inset by 3 mm from the edge of a module / grid (Figure 6).

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`G_local`

Conducting surfaces for `G_local` are implemented as vias (diameter 1mm, pad diameter 1.5 mm) or as pads (diameter 1.5) (Figure 6). A `G_local` surface is spaced 3 mm away from the grid edge and 2 mm away from the paired `v_local` surface in a counter-clockwise direction (Figure 1 and Figure 6).

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`Signal`

`Signal`-conducting surfaces are located along the four edges of a rectangular module. The `Signal` surfaces are implemented as half-vias (1 mm diameter) and corresponding pads on the top and bottom surfaces. The via pads have a size of 1 mm x 1.5 mm (extend 1 mm into the module, given the 0.25 mm recess) (Figure 6). The center to center distance between half-vias is 2 mm along the module edge. There is a 3 mm distance between the corner and the center the first signal via, and consequently a 1 mm gap separates this first signal half-via from the conducting corner surfaces of (`G_global`) (Figure 1 and Figure 6).

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The centers of the `signal` half vias are recessed 0.25 mm away from the nominal grid edge of the module.

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Depending on the length of the edge, and on whether the corner conducting surfaces (`G_global`) are exchanged with `signal` surfaces a minimum and maximum number of available `signal` surfaces can be determined (Table 1)

Table 1. Module size versus the number of available `signal` conducting surfaces.

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Module size (nominal)	Minimum number of <code>signal</code> surfaces	Maximum number of <code>signal</code> surfaces
12 mm x 12 mm	16 ($2*4 + 2*4$)	16 ($2*4 + 2*4$)
12 mm x 24 mm	24 ($2*4 + 2*8$)	28 ($2*4 + 2*10$)
12 mm x 36 mm	32 ($2*4 + 2*12$)	40 ($2*4 + 2 * 16$)
24 mm x 24 mm	32 ($2*8 + 2*8$)	40 ($2*10 + 2*10$)
24 mm x 36 mm	40 ($2*8 + 2*12$)	52 ($2*10 + 2*16$)
24 mm x 48 mm	48 ($2*8 + 2*16$)	64 ($2*10 + 2*22$)
36 mm x 36 mm	48 ($2*12 + 2*12$)	64 ($2*16 + 2*16$)
36 mm x 48 mm	56 ($2*12 + 2*16$)	76 ($2*16 + 2*22$)
48 mm x 48 mm	64 ($2*16 + 2*16$)	88 ($2*22 + 2*22$)

Connecting modules

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One of the main features of *The Standard* is compose-ability and the transitioning between prototype stage and final assembly. Instrumental for the transition is the use of pins and soldering, respectively. This section details how conducting surfaces can be interfaced with one another.

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`G_global -- solder -- G_global`

The four via section of four intersecting corner surfaces form a cavity with 3 mm diameter, The entire cavity can be filled with solder (Figure 7). The solder adheres to the via surfaces and also to the pads. As there are four gaps, the solder usually forms an “X” shape. The cavity can also be filled with a solder-compatible screw which may carry ground (`G_global`). Alternatively, metal rings / metal cylinders can be used to connect the four via section pads or through-holes surface, and thereby reducing the amount of solder required.

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530

`G_global -- fastener -- G_global`

The plated through-hole part of via corner section (`G_global`) can make contact with the body of a conductive fastener, and this fastener connects adjacent modules. Alternatively, connection can also be made through the pads of a via. For example, the head of a screw, or a metal cylinder or a spring can make contact across the corner pads of different modules.

535

`Signal -- pin -- Signal`

Signal surfaces of neighbouring modules can be connected with flexible pins that are embedded within a harness. These pins span the 1.5 mm gap created by the half-vias (2 * 0.5 mm) from each module and the via recess on both modules (2 * 0.25 mm). The type of the flexible pin is an implementation detail. One implementation of the pin was developed and tested along with *The Standard* (Figure 8) and uses common office 24/6 staples. Standard office staples are made from steel and will corrode over time. However, copper and copper-plated 24/6 staples are available that will provide a more reliable surface contact.

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`Signal -- solder -- Signal`

Signal surfaces of neighbouring modules can be bridged with solder. The solder adheres to the two plated half-via through-hole surfaces and the pads. The 0.5 mm half-via recess gap is bridged by solder (Figure 7).

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`v_local – (solder) wire – v_local`

A `v_local` via can be connected to its counterpart on a different module using a wire. The wire can be either soldered directly to the modules. Alternatively, `v_local` on different boards can be connected using a header pin/receptacle combination that is soldered in place.

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Figure 7. Clearance between modules and soldering. Top view of the corner region of an assembly consisting of four interfacing modules. Two modules with no clearance (A, left side) interface with two modules with 0.25 mm clearance (B, right side). The centers of vias are located 0.25 mm away from the edge of the nominal grid for both types of boards. The quarter sections of the vias in the corner have a common center. Via pads are indicated in red, solder is indicated in green.

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Figure 8. Pins interfacing signal and V_{local} surfaces of two two-harnessed modules.

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Top left: Top view of four signal pins interfacing the signal surfaces of two 12 mm x 12 mm modules and a V_{local} pin interfacing with a V_{local} plane.

Top right: Cross section view (along line B indicated in the top view) of the assembly, showing the four pins sitting in a harness.

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Bottom left: Cross section view (along line A indicated in the top view) of the assembly showing the spring-giving shape the connecting pin housed within a cavity of the harness that connects signal surfaces. A pin with a different spring-giving shape connects V_{local} on the module to a power plane. Yes – both pins look like bent staples, because they are bent staples.

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$V_{local} \text{ -- pogo pin -- } V_{local}$

610 The pads at the bottom of V_{local} can interface with spring-loaded (pogo-type) pins, which are seated within a harness. Instead of commercially available pogo-type pins, office staples can be used, when one of the staple legs is used as a spring (Figure 9).

$G_{local} \text{ -- } G_{local}$

615 The same type of connections used for V_{local} can also be used to connect G_{local} on different boards, including soldered header pins. Here, 2-position-2mm-pitch header pins can be used to connect V_{local} and G_{local} of different boards in tandem.

620 **Module Assemblies**

The Standard provides a great amount of flexibility for implementing circuits for different applications. Circuits can be composed and tested solder-free, and “ruggedized” with fasteners within a harness. Finally, modules can be soldered together, so the resulting assembly can be used independently of the harness.

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Un-soldered Assemblies

630 During prototyping, when modules are often relocated, modules can be held in place with pins that also provide electrical connectivity. These pins must be anchored in a harness. The dimensions and embedded functions of the harness is not defined in this document. However, one implementation example is shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, where the harness is shaped to embed signal pins, spring-loaded (pogo-type) pins, and screws.

“Ruggedized” Unsoldered Assemblies

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When stability is required that cannot be provided by signal pins alone, the harness can also provide cavities for fasteners including screws. These “screw-hardened” assemblies provide solder-free resilience towards mechanical stress (Figure 9).

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Soldered Assemblies

645 Very robust module assemblies are obtained when the castellated surfaces of adjacent modules ($signal$ surfaces and G_{global} surfaces) are connected using solder (Figure 7). Some of the G_{global} openings formed can be used as mounting holes in order to fasten module assemblies. For this G_{global} via sections can be either left un-soldered, or only the via pads can be connected by solder, so the fastener can be removed. Solder can also be applied to fuse the corner via sections with the fastener. Other G_{global} corner openings that are not used as mounting holes can be closed using solder.

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Figure 9. Cross section of a harness implementation. A screw and a nut (blue) fastens two modules (grey) with different PCB thicknesses to the harness (beige) with a spacer (green) accommodating the different PCB thicknesses. A metal cylinder (G_global adaptor) is inset into the harness to establish electrical contact between the pads of interfacing modules and the screw (which carries G_global). The position of a G_global plane and a V_local plane are indicated.

670 **Module Assembly Elements**

This section details mechanical properties and features of individual module components and their interactions.

675 *PCB*

PCBs can be obtained in many different thicknesses, depending on the number of layers required.

680 *Stability & Flexibility*

In the context of combining modules, the thickness of a PCB together with the clearance determine the stability and stiffness of the resulting module assembly. With thicker PCBs, there is more surface for the solder to make contact with the castellated vias than on thinner boards. Consequently, soldered module assemblies composed of thicker PCBs have increased stability made user thinner PCBs. The amount of board-to-board clearance has influence on the flexibility of module assemblies, with larger clearances providing more mechanical stability than smaller clearances.

690 *Common Bottom Plane*

As module PCBs can vary in thicknesses (between 1mm and 2 mm), it is necessary to define the vertical alignments of modules. Modules must align so that the bottom faces in an assembly form a common plane. Concomitant to this convention is that only the top faces of modules are usually populated with components. This arrangement ensures that module assemblies can be seated and fastened to plane surfaces. To accommodate module assemblies with different thicknesses, “thickness adapters” in combination with screws can be used to secure the PCBs with different thicknesses.

700 *Thickness Adapters*

It is straight-forwards to solder together modules PCBs with different thicknesses when they sit on a common plane, in order to make a free-standing module assemblies. In harnesses, signal pins have enough flexibility to bridge between modules with different thickness. However, special adapters have to be used to fasten boards with different thicknesses within a harness (Figure 9).

Signal Pins

Many different implementations for signal connectors can be imagined, which bridge the 1.5 mm gap between neighbouring signal surfaces. In addition to making electrical connections, it is desirable that the signal pins also stabilize the modules by pushing them towards and not away from the harness. To this end, 24/6 staples released from a standard stapler and seated inside a harness stabilize the modules very well (Figure 8).

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G_global Openings

720 The 3 mm circular opening formed by four intersecting quarter vias has dual function, distributing ground (*G_global*) between modules, and as feature to fasten modules. The openings may be reinforced with metal rings soldered onto the *G_global* via pads. Furthermore, threaded metal cylinders (standoffs) may be soldered to the board to interface the modules with a screw (Figure 9).

725 *G_global Screws*

Independent of whether they are conductive or not, M3 screws can be used to secure modules to a harness. Screws in combination with thickness adapters (between the top of the module and the screw nut or screw head) facilitate fastening of modules that have different
730 PCB thicknesses (Figure 9).

Future Perspective

735 Modules are a defining feature of the *The Standard*, as they are the physical foundation for modularization of electronics and computation. This document is largely concerned with the description of module dimension and electrical and physical interactions, but does not cover many other aspects that are pertinent to achieving reusable electronics. Some of the more obvious aspect are briefly addressed here. If these aspects are considered important, they will be formalized and annexed to *The Standard*, without impacting the information (for modules) defined in this document.

740

Carrier boards and harnesses

745 Detail on how modules are connected to each other are outlined in this document. However, details about the physical implementation of harnesses have been omitted. This is a deliberate choice, as to leave room for innovation for different modes by which modules can be connected and fastened.

Power

750 The supply voltage level has not been defined by *The Standard*. This makes sense for power electronics components, which often require specific power characteristics. For digital communication a standard voltage may be expected. Common DC supply voltages (12V, 5V, 3.3V and 1.7 V) should be considered suitable, while others should be avoided. This flexibility is not necessarily a big disadvantage, as there is always the option of employing a module that converts between different voltages.

755

Connectors

760 Wires in combination with plugs and receptacles provide options for connecting modules and module assemblies. While carrying power and signal in a physically unified package is often convenient, it negatively impacts compose-ability of electronics. Thus power and signal lines should be separated in most cases. If a connector is used, one should rely on the connectors most commonly used which include 8P8C/6P6P modular connectors, and USB-type connectors. Furthermore simple and easily available connectors that conform with metric/*konstruktive* dimensions should be given precedence, including fork and eye terminals, screw terminal systems, and square (2 mm pitch) header pins.

765

Communication

770 The modules described in this document use conductor-based communication for relaying signals between modules. The implementation of a conductor-based bus systems will be required to efficiently carry information between non-adjacent computing modules within a module assembly. In addition, wireless communication using light and other electro-magnetic waves can extend communication between modules and should be specified in the future.

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Computing

780 Modules that carry MCUs can be combined to create increasingly powerful computing
systems. These systems may collaborate in house appliances, industrial robots, or in data
centers. Having a common form factor, compute modules are exchangeable between these
application environments. Adapting existing and developing new programming languages
and operating systems to work with modular compute units will be necessary to make
785 scalable and distributed computing ubiquitous.

A new type of PCB

790 At present, there appears to be no viable alternative to PCB boards, as this technology has
been matured over decades. Glass-reinforced epox materials are used for the PCB body, but
these materials are “use-once” materials. The metal used for traces, vias and pads is difficult
to recover from PCBs, especially in multilayer boards. Different combinations of material
should be considered to find alternatives from the current type of PCB. Ideally, it should be
straight-forward to separate metal from the board material, and the board material itself
795 should be re-usable.

Diagnosis

800 The reliable identification of broken components and modules is a key requirement for
reusable electronics. Protocols for testing modules and components for functionality would
greatly support the search for broken parts. This is especially true, if these protocols are the
basis of automated testing procedures.

Future electronics

805 In a (future) resource-constrained world, reuse of electronic components is economically
viable. Creating standards and researching technologies for reusing electronic components in
order to make this transition, should be the immediate focus for industry and academia. This
pursuit should focus on “what is desirable” and not “what is to be replaced”, acknowledging
810 that future electronics may be very different from the electronics we use today.

Glossary

- 815 **G_global**
 Electrical ground, which is shared between the modules in an assembly through the corner vias. The corner vias are named G_NW , G_SW, G_SE, G_NE.
- G_local**
820 Ground that enters through vias inset into the module (not through the corner vias of a module). The local vias are named G_nw, G_sw. G_se, G_ne.
- MCU**
 micro controller unit
- 825 **PCB**
 printed circuit board
- 830 **V_local**
 Supply voltage that enters through vias inset into the module. The local vias are named V_nw, V_sw. V_se, V_ne.

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840

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